

A new spot test for the detection of dithiocarbamate fungicides in soil and water

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A new spot test has been developed for the detection of dithiocarbamate fungicides such as mancozeb, propineb and zineb at nkg level in soil and water. The colour formation is based on the decomposition of dithiocarbamate to carbon disulphide which reacts with plumbite in alkaline medium to form a brown complex that finally converts to black lead sulphide. The coloured product exists as a bright brown-black colloidal solution in formaldehyde or glycerin or hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

Dithiocarbamates such as mancozeb, propineb and zineb are being used as agricultural fungicides in grape, cauliflower, potato, chilli, apple, groundnut, paddy etc¹. The pesticide residue concentration is increasing day by day in the environment due to their repeated use for the long period. The pesticide residue analysis involves five steps such as qualitative detection, preconcentration or extraction, separation or clean up, estimation and then identification. Spot test analysis has been found to be extremely simple, inexpensive and useful for the preliminary characterization/detection of the pesticide residue in an environmental matrix.

Therefore, in continuation to our previous work² it was thought worthwhile to develop a new spot test by studying exhaustively a brown colour reaction of dithiocarbamates with plumbite in presence of formaldehyde. This spot test was firstly reported by Feigl and Weisselberg in 1931 and secondly, by Rosen Thaler in 1933 for the detection of carbon disulphide³. It is based on the decomposition of dithiocarbamates into carbon disulphide which produces brown-black colour with plumbite in presence of formaldehyde. Now efforts have been made to utilize this reaction for the detection of dithiocarbamate fungicides in water and soil. The results obtained are described in this paper.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Aluminium heating block, U-tube, micro-test tube, Whatman[®] No.1 filter paper were used.

Chemicals and reagents :

Mancozeb (75% WP) (Modern Insecticides Ltd.,

India); propineb (70% WP) (Bayer India (P) Ltd., India); sodium diethyl dithiocarbamate (97%) (CDH (P.) Ltd., India); zineb (75% WP) (Indofil Chemicals Company, India); lead monoxide (Qualigens Fine Chemicals, India); formaldehyde solution (37–41% w/v) in water were used. All other reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Preparation of solutions :

Plumbite reagent (Pbt) was prepared by dissolving lead monoxide (1 g) in 32% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution. The homogeneous suspensions of 0.75% mancozeb, 0.70% propineb and 0.75% zineb were prepared in distilled water (DW). Solutions of 1% sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (NaDDC), 40% sucrose, 10% ascorbic acid, 40% glucose, 2% starch, 40% hydroxylamine hydrochloride, 5% potassium permanganate and 10 M sulphuric acid were also prepared in DW.

Preparation of indicator paper :

The paper strip of Whatman[®] No.1 filter paper (1 × 4 cm) was dipped in a watch glass containing the reagent, the excess reagent was drained (draw) off and then the semi-dried paper was used for detection. Always freshly prepared indicator paper was used.

Collection of soil samples :

Loam soil from Jattari village in tehsil Khair, clay loam from tehsil Sikandra-Rao and from the barren fields around Aligarh Muslim University (A.M.U.), silty clay loam from tehsil Atrauli from the fields in the neighbourhood of sankra bus-stand about 3 km from the river bank, agricultural farm soil from A.M.U., were collected from district Aligarh (U.P.). Red soil was col-

lected from Bhubaneswar (Orissa). The sampling was done during the month of April. To obtain a composite sample, small portions of soil were collected from the desired depth (0–15 cm or more) with Khurpi from 10–15 well distributed spots (from each sampling Unit i.e. a plot) after scrapping off the surface litter. A V-shaped cut (up to the plough layer) was made and a uniformly 1.5 cm (approx) thick slice was taken out. The soil collected in this manner was thoroughly mixed on a polythene sheet or concrete floor and bulk reduced by quartering and about 500 g of the composite sample was retained. The soil was quickly air dried in shade at room temperature and put in polythene bag with suitable description and identification marks by tagging.

Detection procedure :

Detection in solution :

Analyte (0.1 ml of 1%) was taken in a micro-test tube, 3–4 drops of the reagent were added to it and after thorough mixing the colour developed at room temperature ($25 \pm 3^\circ$) and at elevated temperature ($55 \pm 5^\circ$) was noted. In second attempt, the analyte was treated with one drop of dilute sulphuric acid (10 M), the reagent was added and the colour developed was noted. In third attempt, the mixture of the analyte and the sulphuric acid was briefly heated, then the reagent was added and the colour developed was recorded.

The lower limit of detection (LOD) was measured by using the known volume (0.1 ml) of the standard analyte solutions of different concentrations in the later procedure.

Vapour phase detection :

Indicator paper detection :

The analyte solution (0.1 ml of 1%) was taken in a micro-test tube. The moisture contents were removed by heating at $50\text{--}70^\circ$. The contents were cooled to room temperature and a drop of conc. H_2SO_4 was added to it. The indicator paper was hung in the test tube. The contents were heated at $25\text{--}150^\circ$. If indicator paper turns brown-black the dithiocarbamate is present.

The LOD was measured by taking the known volume (0.1 ml) of the standard solutions of the analyte of different concentrations.

U-tube detection :

The analyte solution (0.1 ml of 1%) was taken in a test tube A (9.8×1.2 cm i.d.) jointed with a side U-tube³ (16.9×0.3 cm, i.d.). The moisture was removed by heating, the contents were cooled to room temperature, one drop of 10 M H_2SO_4 was added to it and the reagent

(0.1 ml) was taken in the side U-tube. The tube A was stoppered and heated at $60\text{--}150^\circ$ to bubble the fumes (CS_2) through U-tube containing the reagent. The change in colour of the reagent was noted after one minute.

The LOD was measured by taking the known volume (0.1 ml) of the standard solutions of the analyte of different concentrations.

Detection in soil :

A soil sample (10 mg) was taken in a micro-test tube, dithiocarbamate solution (0.1 ml of 1%) was added to it and the above procedures were used to detect the dithiocarbamate.

A soil sample (2 g) was taken in a watch glass, it was treated with dithiocarbamate solution (2 ml of 1%) and the sample was dried at room temperature. A portion of the treated soil was tested for dithiocarbamate using the above procedures. This study was conducted for 10–15 days and the dithiocarbamate residue was found to be present. The LOD in soils was measured by adding known volume of standard solutions of dithiocarbamate under study in the known weight of soil sample.

Results and discussion

The following results were obtained when the colour reaction of dithiocarbamates was studied with several reagents under different conditions :

(A) The analyte was treated directly with plumbite, (B) the analyte was treated with 10 M H_2SO_4 and then plumbite was added to it, and (C) the analyte was treated with 10 M H_2SO_4 , briefly heated and then plumbite was added to it. The detection was also performed by using the following admixtures as the reagent under aforesaid conditions : (1a) formaldehyde alone, (1b) formaldehyde first and then plumbite, (1c) plumbite first and then formaldehyde, (1d) plumbite-formaldehyde (2 : 1), (1e) formaldehyde-plumbite (3 : 1), (1f) plumbite-formaldehyde (3:1), (2a) sucrose alone, (2b) sucrose first and then plumbite, (2c) plumbite first and then sucrose, (2d) plumbite-sucrose (2 : 1) , (2e) sucrose-plumbite (3 : 1), (2f) plumbite-sucrose (3 : 1), (3a) glucose alone, (3b) glucose first and then plumbite, (3c) plumbite first and then glucose, (3d) plumbite-glucose (2 : 1), (3e) glucose-plumbite (3 : 1), (3f) plumbite-glucose (3 : 1), (4a) starch alone, (4b) starch first and then plumbite, (4c) plumbite first and then starch, (4d) plumbite-starch (2 : 1) , (4e) starch-plumbite (3 : 1) , (4f) plumbite-starch (3 : 1), (5a) ascorbic acid alone, (5b) ascorbic acid first and then plumbite, (5c) plumbite first and then ascorbic acid, (5d) plumbite-ascorbic acid (2 : 1), (5e) ascorbic

acid-plumbite (3 : 1), (5f) plumbite-ascorbic acid (3 : 1), (6a) dimethylamine alone, (6b) dimethylamine first and then plumbite, (6c) plumbite first and then dimethylamine, (6d) plumbite-dimethylamine (2 : 1), (6e) dimethylamine-plumbite (3 : 1), (6f) plumbite-dimethylamine (3 : 1), (7a) silica gel alone, (7b) silica gel first and then plumbite, (7c) plumbite first and then silica gel, (7d) plumbite-silica gel (2 : 1), (7e) silica gel-plumbite (3 : 1), (7f) plumbite-silica gel (3 : 1), (8a) glycerin alone, (8b) glycerin first and then plumbite, (8c) plumbite first and then glycerin, (8d) plumbite-glycerin (2 : 1), (8e) glycerin-plumbite (3 : 1) (8f) plumbite-glycerin (3 : 1), (9a) soap alone, (9b) soap first and then plumbite, (9c) plumbite first and then soap, (9d) plumbite-soap (2 : 1), (9e) soap-plumbite (3 : 1), (9f) plumbite-soap (3 : 1), (10a) gum alone, (10b) gum first and then plumbite, (10c) plumbite first and then gum, (10d) plumbite-gum (2 : 1), (10e) gum-plumbite (3 : 1), (10f) plumbite-gum (3 : 1), (11a) paraffin oil alone, (11b) paraffin oil first and then plumbite, (11c) plumbite first and then paraffin oil, (11d) plumbite-paraffin oil (2 : 1), (11e) paraffin oil-plumbite (3 : 1), (11f) plumbite-paraffin oil (3 : 1), (12a) fevicol alone, (12b) fevicol first and then plumbite, (12c) plumbite first and then fevicol, (12d) plumbite-fevicol (2 : 1), (12e) fevicol-plumbite (3 : 1), (12f) plumbite-fevicol (3 : 1), (13a) hydroxylamine hydrochloride alone, (13b) hydroxylamine hydrochloride first and then plumbite, (13c) plumbite first and then hydroxylamine hydrochloride, (13d) plumbite-hydroxylamine hydrochloride (2 : 1), (13e) hydroxylamine hydrochloride-plumbite (3 : 1), (13f) plumbite-hydroxylamine hydrochloride (3 : 1), (14a) aluminium oxide acidic alone, (14b) aluminium oxide acidic first and then plumbite, (14c) plumbite first and then aluminium oxide acidic, (14d) plumbite-aluminium oxide acidic (2 : 1), (14e) aluminium oxide acidic-plumbite (3 : 1), (14f) plumbite-aluminium oxide acidic (3 : 1), (15a) aluminium oxide basic alone, (15b) aluminium oxide basic first and then plumbite, (15c) plumbite first and then aluminium oxide basic, (15d) plumbite-aluminium oxide basic (2 : 1), (15e) aluminium oxide basic-plumbite (3 : 1), (15f) plumbite-aluminium oxide basic (3 : 1), (16a) potassium permanganate alone, (16b) potassium permanganate first and then plumbite, (16c) plumbite first and then potassium permanganate, (16d) plumbite-potassium permanganate (2 : 1), (16e) potassium permanganate-plumbite (3 : 1), (16f) plumbite-potassium permanganate (3 : 1).

An attempt was also made to detect the dithiocarbamates by using different technologies and reagents. The colour and (LOD) (nkg) of NaDDC, mancozeb, propineb

and zineb are obtained by solution state test, vapour phase – (u) tube test, vapour phase indicator paper test are given at first, second and third places in first parenthesis using plumbite-formaldehyde, second parenthesis using plumbite-glycerin and third parenthesis using plumbite-hydroxylamine hydrochloride respectively : NaDDC (Br 100, Br 100, Br 100), (Br 100, Br 100, Br 100), (Br 100, Br 100, Br 100); mancozeb (LBr 7.5, VLBr 75, Br 75), (VLBr 7.5, LBr 75, Br 75), (VLBr 7.5, Br 75, LBr 75); propineb (VLBr 7.0, Br 70, Br 70), (LBr 7.0, Br 70, Br 70), (LBr 7.0, Br 70, Br 70) and zineb (LBr 7.5, Br 75, Br 75), (Br 7.5, Br 75, Br 75), (LBr 7.5, LBr 75, Br 75). Abbreviations are defined as Bl = black, Br = brown, D = dark, Gr = green, L = light, Nc = no colour, R = Red, V = very, Y = yellow.

The following results were obtained when dithiocarbamate detected in A.M.U. farm soil using different techniques and reagents. The colour and (LOD) (nkg) obtained by solution state test, vapour phase – (u) tube test, vapour phase indicator paper test are given at first, second and third places in the parenthesis i.e. Sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (DBr-LDBr 100, Br-VLBr 100, Br-VLBr 100), (Nc, LBr 1000, Br-VLBr 100), (DBr 1000, Nc, Nc), (DBr 1000, LBr 1000, Br 1000), (DBr 1000, RBr 1000, Br 1000), (DBr 1000, Nc, Nc), (Nc, Nc, Nc), (DBr-LDBr 100, LBr 100, Br 100), (DBr 1000, Nc, Nc), (DBr 1000, Nc, Nc), (DBr 1000, Nc, Nc), (Nc, VLBr 1000, VLBr 1000), (DBr 1000, DBr-Br 100, DBr-LDBr 100), (DBr 1000, LBl 1000, Br 1000), (DBr 1000, LBl 1000, Br 1000), (GrBr 1000, Nc, Nc), with plumbite-formaldehyde, plumbite-sucrose, plumbite-glucose, plumbite-starch, plumbite-ascorbic acid, plumbite-dimethylamine, plumbite-silica gel, plumbite-glycerin, plumbite-soap, plumbite-gum, plumbite-fevicol, plumbite-paraffin, plumbite-hydroxylamine hydrochloride, plumbite-aluminium oxide acidic, plumbite-aluminium oxide basic, plumbite-potassium permanganate respectively. Mancozeb (Bl-LBl 75, DBr-LBl 75, DBr-Br 75), (DBr-LBl 75, DBr-VLBr 75, DBr-VLBr 75), (DBr 750, Nc, Nc), (DBr-LDBr 75, DBr 750, Br 750), (LBl 75, Br 750, DBr 750), (DBr 75, LBr 750, DBr 750), (DBr 75, LBl 750, Bl 750), (DBr 75, LBl 75, Br 75), (DBr 75, Nc, Nc), (LDBr 75, Nc, Nc), (LDBr 75, Nc, Nc), (DBr 75, LBl 750, LBr 750), (DBr 75, LBl 75, LBl 75), (DBr 75, LBr 75, LBr 75), (DBr 75, Br 75, LBr 75), (VDBr 750, Nc, Nc) with above reagents. Zineb (DBr-LDBr 75, Bl-LBr 75, Bl-LBr 75), (DBr 75, LDBr 75, LDBr 75), (DBr-LDBr75, DBr-Br 75, Bl-Br 75), with plumbite-formaldehyde, plumbite-glycerin, plumbite-hydroxylamine hydrochloride respectively and Propineb (DBr-LDBr 70, Bl-

LBr 70, DBr-Br 70), (LDBr 70, DBr-Br 70, BI-LDBr 70), (LDBr 70, DBr-Br 70, BI-LDBr 70) with above reagents.

The results of detection of zineb and propineb in different types of soils are summarised as below. The colour and (LOD) (nkg) obtained by solution state spot test, (u) tube and indicator paper spot test of vapour phase are given at first, second and third places in the parenthesis i.e. Zineb (VDBr-LBI 75, DBr-LBI 75, DBr-Br 75), (VDBr-Br 7.5, DBr-LBI 75, DBr-LDBr 75), (VDBr-LBI 75, DBr-LBI 75, DBr-Br 75) in loam; (DBr-Br 7.5, DBr-Br 75, DBr-Br 75), (VDBr-Br 7.5, DBr-Br 75, DBr-LDBr 75), (DBr-Br 7.5, DBr-Br 75, DBr-Br 75) in silt clay loam; (DBr-LBI 75, DBr-Br 75, DBr-Br 75), (VDBr-Br 7.5, DBr-LBI 75, DBr-LDBr 75), (DBr-LBI 75, DBr-Br 75, DBr-LDBr 75) in clay loam (A.M.U.); (VDBr-LBI 75, DBr-LBI 75, DBr-LBr 75), (VDBr-LBI 75, DBr-Br 75, DBr-LDBr 75), (DBr-LBI 75, DBr-LBI 75, DBr-LBr 75) in clay loam (Sikandra Rao); (VDBr-LBI 75, DBr-LBI 75, DBr-Br 75), (VDBr-LBI 75, DBr-LBI 75, DBr-Br 75), (DBr-LBI 75, DBr-LBI 75, DBr-Br 75) in red soil using plumbite-formaldehyde, plumbite-glycerin, plumbite-hydroxylamine hydrochloride reagents respectively. Propineb (VDBr-DBr 70, DBr-LBI 70, DBr-Dy 7.0), (VDBr-DBr 7.0, DBr-LBI 70, DBr-LBI 70), (DBr-LDBr 70, DBr-LBI 70, DBr-LBI 70) in loam soil; (DBr-Br 7.0, DBr-Br 70, DBr-Dy 7.0), (VDBr-Br 7.0, DBr-Br 70, DBr-LBI 70), (DBr-Br 7.0, DBr-Br 70, DBr-LDBr 70) in silt clay loam; (VDBr-LBI 70, DBr-Br 70, DBr-Dy 7.0), (VDBr-LBI 7.0, DBr-LBr 70, DBr-LBr 70), (VDBr-LBI 70, DBr-Br 70, DBr-LBr 70) in clay loam (A.M.U.); (VDBr-LBI 70, DBr-Br 70, DBr-Dy 7.0), (VDBr-LBI 70, DBr-Br 70, DBr-LBr 70), (VDBr-LBI 70, DBr-Br 70, DBr-LBr 70) in clay loam (Sikandra Rao) and (VDBr-LBI 70, DBr-Br 70, DBr-Dy 7.0), (VDBr-LBI 70, DBr-LBr 70, DBr-LBr 70), (VDBr-LBI 70, DBr-Br 70, DBr-LBr 70) in red soil using above reagents.

It has been reported⁴ that xanthates, thioxanthates dithiocarbamates, thiuram disulphides etc. on acidification liberate carbon disulphide. Carbon disulphide is converted into trithiocarbonate on treatment with alkali hydroxide :

The trithiocarbonate reacts with heavy metals to give insoluble salts, which can be readily decomposed with the formation of sulphide. Carbon disulphide can be quickly converted into lead sulphide by treatment with conc. caustic alkali and a plumbite solution. However, it

is not applicable at trace level of carbon disulphide. Feigl has remarked that the formation of trithiocarbonate and hence of PbS can be accelerated by formaldehyde for a reason that is not well understood⁵. Acetaldehyde, benzaldehyde, arabinose, glucose and lactose show the same effect. This action affords a means of detecting small amount of carbon disulphide. Hence the spot test under study seems to be promising for the nanokilogram detection of dithiocarbamates fungicides in environmental samples.

First paragraph shows that NaDDC does not give colour with plumbite and it produces colour with plumbite in presence of dilute acid at room temperature as well as at elevated temperature. However, mancozeb produces colour directly with plumbite. It may be due to the fact that NaDDC does not split off to CS₂ without acid while mancozeb gives CS₂ without acid. This observation is on line with the literature⁶ i.e. dithiocarbamates are unstable in acidic medium and heavy metal dithiocarbamates are readily decomposed to give sulphides. It is also clear from the aforesaid results that the bright colour was obtained with reagent plumbite-formaldehyde (3 : 1) provided that plumbite was added first and then formaldehyde i.e. if formaldehyde was followed by plumbite good bright colour was not produced. The admixtures of plumbite-formaldehyde also produce bright colour. The bright colour was also obtained when glycerin or hydroxylamine hydrochloride was used in place of formaldehyde. It was also observed that the rate of settling of brown-black precipitate is in the following sequence :

Paraffin < CCl₄ < gum < fevicol < detergent < HCl < ethanol < distilled water < NaOH < glycerin < formaldehyde.

Hence it seems that the fine particles of plumbite sulphide exist as colloidal particle in glycerin and formaldehyde. Thus the role of glycerin or formaldehyde or hydroxylamine hydrochloride is to form bright brown-black colloidal system at nkg level of dithiocarbamates. The colour reaction under study is more sensitive in solution state than vapour state.

It was also observed that the common impurities such as hardness causing substances, detergent, silt, clay and soil do not produce any colour with the reagent. Therefore, spot test under study can be successfully used for the detection of dithiocarbamates in soil and water.

Conclusion :

The spot test under study can be successfully utilized for the trace level detection of dithiocarbamate fungi-

cides in water and soil. It is 10 times sensitive (LOD = 7.5 nkg for mancozeb) in presence of formaldehyde or glycerin or hydroxylamine hydrochloride than that (LOD = 75 nkg for mancozeb) in presence of acetaldehyde, benzaldehyde, arabinose, glucose, lactose, starch etc. This observation contradicts the remark reported in the Feigl's book⁵.

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